

ADVANCED COMPOSITES MANUFACTURED VIA DRY POWDER PREPREGGING

T. A. Bullions¹, A.C. Loos¹, and J.E. McGrath²

¹*Department of Engineering Science and Mechanics, Mail Code: 0219, 219 Norris Hall, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, Blacksburg, VA 24061-0219, USA*

²*Department of Chemistry, Mail Code: 0212, 2111 Hahn Hall, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, Blacksburg, VA 24061-0212, USA*

SUMMARY: Work at the National Science Foundation Science and Technology Center (NSF S&TC) for High Performance Polymeric Adhesives and Composites at Virginia Tech has focused on the emerging technology of dry powder prepregging as a method of overcoming the high-melt viscosities of high-performance polymers. Three NSF S&TC projects utilizing dry powder prepregging to manufacture advanced composites are discussed. The effects of prepregging, processing, and polymer particle parameters on the consolidation quality of carbon fiber composites fabricated from dry powder coated prepreg will be examined. The first project brings forth several important questions concerning the influence of PEEK powder particle size on composite consolidation quality. The second project determines the optimal consolidation pressure and hold time for GR-01 PPS/G30-500 composites. Finally, dry powder prepregging enables the manufacture of and measurement of the mechanical properties of carbon fiber-reinforced phenylethynyl terminated Ultem™ composites.

KEYWORDS: dry powder prepregging, particle size, consolidation pressure, on-line consolidation, poly(phenylene sulfide), poly(ether ether ketone), phenylethynyl, Ultem™

INTRODUCTION

Development of high-performance polymers with improved mechanical properties, increased thermal and oxidative stability, and greater solvent resistance will allow fiber-reinforced polymeric composites (FRPC)s to be utilized in service environments too harsh for previous FRPCs. Unfortunately, these improvements come with high-melt viscosities. Attempting to overcome high viscosities by increasing processing temperature and pressure may degrade the polymer and/or damage the fiber structure. Furthermore, the excellent solvent resistance of these polymers often eliminates the option of solvent prepregging due to their insolubilities.

Work at the National Science Foundation Science and Technology Center (NSF S&TC) for High Performance Polymeric Adhesives and Composites at Virginia Tech has focused on the emerging technology of dry powder prepregging (DPP) as a method of overcoming the high-

melt viscosities of high-performance polymers [1, 2]. The DPP facility developed at Virginia Tech uses an electrostatic fluidized bed (EFB) deposition chamber or a minimal dry powder prepregging system (MDPPS) for use with small samples of developmental polymers or powders that do not fluidize well. The MDPPS is capable of quality composite production from polymer samples as small as 50 g and has been used extensively in the NSF S&TC for the performance verification of state-of-the-art polymers. Three NSF S&TC projects utilizing DPP to manufacture advanced composites are discussed. The effects of prepregging, processing, and polymer particle parameters on the consolidation quality of FRPCs fabricated from dry powder coated prepreg will be examined.

Dry powder prepregging overcomes high-melt viscosity problems by reducing the polymer flow distance; polymer particles adhered to fibers are only required to flow distances on the order of microns during composite consolidation, rather than distances on the order of millimeters as seen in resin transfer molding or resin film infusion [3]. Therefore, whether the size of the attached polymer particles influences the consolidation process and the resultant mechanical properties comes into question. Miller, et al. [3], and Tang, et al. [4], developed models predicting the effects of particle size on the consolidation process and resultant consolidation quality. The first of three projects examines the influence of particle size on composites manufactured from MDPPS produced towpreg (powder coated fiber tow); consolidation quality was measured with ultrasonic inspection and mechanical properties.

The second project successfully utilized the MDPPS in the development of a consolidation cycle for carbon fiber-reinforced poly(phenylene sulfide) (PPS) composites via a designed experiment. Several different grades of PPS are available, and each grade requires different processing conditions to achieve a well-consolidated composite; this project studied grade GR-01. The key variables in composite processing are temperature, consolidation pressure, and time. There is a relatively small window between the temperature at which GR-01 reaches a processable viscosity and at which it degrades. Therefore, consolidation pressure and time were chosen as the experimental variables. A design of experiments method was used to produce a test matrix of nine different combinations of pressure and hold time. The consolidation quality of each panel was measured qualitatively via ultrasonic inspection and optical microscopy and quantitatively by apparent interlaminar shear strength (AISS). These results were used to determine an optimal consolidation pressure and time.

The third project focuses on the development of 3,000 g/mol phenylethynyl-terminated Ultem™ (3kPETU) as a high-performance composite matrix material. The cured polymer has a T_g of about 250 °C along with good thermo-oxidative stability, solvent resistance, and mechanical properties [5]. However, the rheological behavior of 3kPETU places doubt in the successful production of thick parts via resin infusion or transfer methods [6]. Selection of powder prepregging was augmented by the fact that this oligomer is readily synthesized in a powder form. The limited quantity and large particle size distribution of this developmental material inhibited the use of the EFB, which requires 400 g to 500 g of material to operate. Thus, the MDPPS was employed to coat unsized, 12k, G30-500 carbon fiber tow (Toho Carbon Fibers, Inc.) with 3kPETU powder. This paper discusses attempts to filament wind rings with 3kPETU/G30-500 towpreg and presents the results of mechanical property tests performed on 3kPETU/G30-500 composite panels manufactured from this towpreg.

EXPERIMENTAL

Particle Size Study

Sieving

Poly(ether ether ketone) (PEEK) powder, from ICI, was wet sieved to produce three particle size distributions: greater than 106 μm (>106), 53 μm to 106 μm (53/106), and less than 53 μm (<53). Number 140 and 270 Tyler screens were used for sieving; the corresponding hole widths for screen numbers 140 and 270 are 106 μm and 53 μm , respectively. Particle size distributions were measured with a Horiba LA-700 particle analyzer.

Composite Manufacture

The MDPPS was used to coat 12k, G30-500 carbon fiber tow with the four distributions: as-received, >106 , 53/106, and <53 . The coating process is described in Ref. 6. Unidirectional panels were consolidated from these four batches of towpreg and APC-2 (PEEK/AS4) prepreg using the same process. Consolidation took place under a pressure of 1.4 MPa. The mold temperature was ramped at 3 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ from room temperature to 380 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, held for 5 minutes, cooled to 260 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, held for 30 minutes, and finally cooled to room temperature at 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. The hold at 260 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ was implemented for PEEK crystallization.

Consolidation Evaluation

Each panel was imaged ultrasonically via a pulse-echo arrangement utilizing a 15 MHz transducer with a focal length of 12.7 mm. These raster patterns, or C-scans, of the intensity of the ultrasonic signal that is transmitted through the panel and then reflected back through the panel to the transducer allow qualitative assessment of panel consolidation quality.

Both longitudinal flexural (LF) and transverse flexural (TF) testing were performed according to ASTM D 790-92 following the four-point bend method (Test Method II - Procedure A) with a span-to-depth ratio of 32:1. The AISS tests were performed according to ASTM D 2344-84 for flat laminates with a span-to-depth ratio of 4:1.

PPS Consolidation Study

Composite Manufacture

The powdered PPS contained particle sizes ranging from 5 μm to 800 μm ; the relatively large particles prevented fluidization. Therefore, the MDPPS was utilized to coat the PPS powder onto 12k, G30-500 carbon fiber tow. Unidirectional panels were manufactured following nearly identical consolidation schedules. The schedules commenced with a 5 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ ramp to 315 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ followed by a hold for a length of time determined by the pressure and hold time test matrix. The consolidation process was completed with a 5 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ cooling to room temperature during which the applied pressure was maintained. The first unidirectional composite panel consolidated at 0.965 MPa with a 12 minute hold was poorly consolidated. These consolidation conditions were chosen from an initial, less complex plan to determine the optimal consolidation conditions. Consequently, the method of designed experiments was used to develop an experimental test matrix to find the best consolidation conditions [7].

Test Matrix Development

Using the first panel as a reference, the test matrix shown in Fig. 1a was developed. The corner values for consolidation pressure were chosen to be 0.965 MPa and 1.79 MPa resulting

in a center pressure of 1.38 MPa. The corner values for time were chosen to be 12 and 24 minutes resulting in a center time of 18 minutes. The extreme values, those pressures and times “outside the box”, were calculated with Eqns 1 and 2.

$$\begin{aligned} extreme_{\max} &= center + (\max - center) \cdot \sqrt{2} \\ extreme_{\min} &= center - (center - \min) \cdot \sqrt{2} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

(2)

The first panels processed from this matrix indicated, based on ultrasonic inspection, that the best consolidation conditions might lie above or near the upper edge of the test matrix. Therefore, the test matrix was restructured around a center value of 1.97 MPa and 18 minutes, one of the already manufactured panels. The corner values for consolidation pressure in this test matrix became 2.55 MPa and 1.38 MPa, while the hold times remained the same. The recalculated extreme pressure values were 1.14 MPa and 2.79 MPa. Due to a towpreg shortage, the 1.38 MPa / 18 minute panel from the first test matrix was substituted for the 1.14 MPa / 18 minute panel. This substitution sacrifices some accuracy in the results of the predicted consolidation conditions. The restructured test matrix is shown in Fig. 1b.

Consolidation Evaluation

Each consolidated panel was ultrasonically imaged in a manner similar to the PEEK/G30-500 panels. After imaging, five specimens for optical microscopy inspection and ten specimens for AISS tests were cut from each panel. AISS tests complied with ASTM D2344-84.

Fig. 1a. Original Test Matrix

Fig. 1b. Restructured Test Matrix

PETU Composite Study

On-line Consolidation

A Composites Machine Company computer-controlled filament winding system was used to wind three rings with 3kPETU/G30-500 towpreg on a 146 mm diameter mandrel. An air torch aimed at the pressure roller / mandrel nip point provided the necessary heat for polymer flow. The first two rings were wound with towpreg having a resin volume fraction of about 0.40. The third ring was wound with towpreg having a resin volume fraction of about 0.44. Other winding conditions are given in Table 1. The three rings were not postcured.

Table 1: On-line Consolidation Conditions

Parameter	Ring #1	Ring #2	Ring #3
Winding Speed (RPM)	0.5	0.1	0.5
Winding Speed (mm/min)	229	46	229
Torch Temperature (°C)	677	718	704

Composite Manufacture

Towpreg similar to that used in the ring winding was consolidated into unidirectional 152.4 mm square composite panels under a fluctuating pressure of 1.2 to 1.4 MPa, which was applied prior to the mold temperature reaching 50 °C. The mold temperature was ramped from room temperature to 250 °C at 5 °C/min followed by a ramp at 3 °C/min to 350 °C. This 100 °C range contains 3kPETU's minimum viscosity region before chain growth and crosslinking commence on a large scale [6]. The mold was held at 350 °C for 60 minutes prior to cooling to room temperature at 4 °C/min. Panels were manufactured for LF and TF tests, AISS tests, and Mode I and Mode II fracture toughness tests. Lay-up of the fracture toughness panels included 152.4 mm x 40 mm x 12.7 μm pieces of DuPont Kapton[®] polyimide film to act as starter cracks during testing. The film was placed between the middle two plies after the film was coated on both sides with Dexter Frekote[®] 33 mold release.

Consolidation Evaluation

Ultrasonic imaging following composite panel manufacture and optical microscopy following mechanical testing provided qualitative assessment of panel consolidation. Flexural and AISS testing followed previously cited procedures. Mode I fracture toughness tests utilized the double cantilever beam (DCB) method, and Mode II fracture toughness tests utilized the end-notch flexure (ENF) method. Both procedures are detailed in Ref. 8.

RESULTS

Particle Size Study

Particle Size Analysis

From the as-received PEEK, three distinct particle ranges were obtained; each exhibited a Gaussian distribution. Particle size analysis results for each batch are given in Fig. 2a - d.

Consolidation Evaluation

The ultrasonic C-scans showed that as the median particle size decreased, the homogeneity and consolidation quality of the panels decreased. The quality of the APC-2 panel was comparable to that of the >106 panel. The quality of the control panel was comparable to the <53 panel. The 53/106 panel consolidation quality fell between that of these two pairs.

Fiber volume fractions ranging from 0.54 to 0.63 were estimated from towpreg mass fractions. The poor consolidation of the control and <53 panels is seen in the LF strength results, otherwise, differences in LF strength (Fig. 3) of the powder prepregged composites did not closely follow trends of either the C-scan results or fiber volume fractions; little difference was seen in their LF moduli (~120 GPa). The LF modulus of the APC-2 panel was approximately 150 GPa. The APC-2 displayed a higher TF modulus (~12 GPa) and strength (Fig. 3) than the powder prepregged composites, which displayed little variation in TF modulus (~9 GPa). The TF strength (Fig. 3) displayed the only observable trend in mechanical properties in this study. The TF strength decreased with decreasing particle size, except that the <53 panel had a higher TF strength than the control panel. The TF strength results agree with the observations made with ultrasonic inspection. The APC-2 composite also had the highest AISS (~118

MPa). The composites fabricated from the three particle size ranges showed no significant difference in AISS (~82 MPa). The control panel had the lowest AISS (~75 MPa).

Fig. 2a. Particle Size Distribution - Control

Fig. 2b. Particle Size Distribution - >106

Fig. 2c. Particle Size Distribution - 53/106

Fig. 2d. Particle Size Distribution - <53

The better matrix and fiber/matrix interface dominated properties (TF and AISS) of the APC-2 composite are believed to be due to the existence of crystallinity nucleating agents and an optimized interface between the PEEK and AS4. The decrease in TF strength with decreasing particle size may be attributed to particle agglomeration seen during inspection of the towpreg with scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Agglomeration was most evident in the control and <53 towpreg, which had the smallest median particle size of the four batches. Increased agglomeration results in greater continuous dry fiber distances than would exist if particles remained separate. Thus, consolidation may be poor due to insufficient fiber wet-out.

This study of particle size effect on mechanical properties brings forth several relevant questions. In all cases, panel consolidation could have been improved significantly. Could the consolidation be improved with processing schedule changes? If so, would these changes erase the effects of particle size and therefore make particle size irrelevant? Is agglomeration a result of the MDPPS? Can agglomeration be avoided? To better understand any direct effects, versus indirect effects such as agglomeration, of particle size on mechanical properties, towpreg with more uniformly dispersed particles is needed.

Fig. 3. Flexural Properties vs. Particle Size Distribution

PPS Consolidation Study

Consolidation Evaluation

Ultrasonic inspection allows only qualitative evaluation, thus the level of apparent consolidation quality was categorized into one of three groups. The differentiation is shown in Fig. 4. Despite poor panel consolidation exhibited by ultrasonic inspection, optical microscopy displayed resin rich areas, but no sign of voids in any of the panels. All of the panels appeared relatively equivalent on a microscopic scale. However, only about one percent of the total available cross-sectional area in each panel was inspected.

Fig. 4. Consolidation Quality of PPS / G30-500 Composite Panels

The panel consolidated under a pressure of 1.96 MPa with a hold time of 26.5 min produced the maximum measured AISS of 50 MPa. The AISS results from this and the other consolidation conditions are shown in Fig. 4, which shows that the C-scan results correlate well with the AISS results. The average AISS for each specimen was entered into the data analysis program JMP [9], which was used to calculate a two-dimensional contour plot with consolidation pressure and time as the axes (Fig. 5). The arcs and circles are lines of constant AISS. This contour plot shows the maximum AISS to be located at a consolidation pressure

of 1.93 MPa and a 22 minute hold time. The calculated optimal consolidation conditions lie well within the restructured test matrix (Fig. 1b), hence these conditions are expected to result in consistently well consolidated GR-01 PPS/G30-500 composites.

Fig. 5. Contour Plot For Optimal Apparent Interlaminar Shear Strength

PETU Composite Study

On-line Consolidation

The rings were wound to a thickness of approximately 1.5 mm. Ring one contained lots of dry fiber, and the layers of the ring could be peeled away indicating poor consolidation. By reducing the winding speed and slightly increasing the torch temperature, a much better ring was produced during the second winding. Whereas the first ring was dry and exhibited little resin flow, the second ring exhibited resin flow and better consolidation, although some of the top layer of the ring could still be peeled away. The third ring exhibited good consolidation and excess resin was apparent at the ring edges. The higher towpreg resin content appeared to have significantly improved consolidation.

Improved consolidation from ring one to ring three was apparent by increased stiffness and resin flow transverse to the fiber direction. The difference in consolidation quality could be felt by flexing the rings and feeling the lack of intimate contact, or bonding, between layers in ring one versus the solid feel of ring three. The width of ring one was about the same as that of the towpreg. But, the widths of rings two and three were greater, with that of ring three being about twice the width of ring one. It was apparent that the better resin flow allowed the fibers to move transverse to the circumferential direction under the pressure roller. In summary, from ring one to ring three: resin flow improved, ring width increased, resin content at the ring edges increased, ring stiffness increased, and consolidation improved.

Composite Panel Consolidation Evaluation

Ultrasonic imaging through the thickness of the composite panels and optical microscopy of panel cross sections indicated good consolidation with some resin rich regions. The results of the flexural and AISS tests are given in Table 2. SEM inspection of both LF and TF fracture surfaces displayed excellent fiber/matrix adhesion and matrix deformation, indicating energy absorption by the matrix. All but one of the twelve AISS specimens exhibited horizontal shear crack propagation from the edge inward.

The critical Mode I strain energy release rate (G_{IC}) for the 3kPETU/G30-500 composite measured via the DCB test, and the critical Mode II strain energy release rate (G_{IIc}) measured

via the ENF test are given in Table 2. Carbon fiber-reinforced composites fabricated with a 3kPETU matrix offer substantial increases in toughness over traditional epoxies and compare well with toughened epoxies and other crosslinkable thermoplastics [8]. Thermoplastic matrices offer greater toughness than 3kPETU, but do not have the high-temperature stability and solvent resistance of 3kPETU. Inspection with SEM revealed matrix deformation and minimal bare fiber in the G_{IC} and G_{IIC} fracture surfaces indicating good fiber/matrix adhesion.

Table 2. 3kPETU/G30-500 Composite Mechanical Properties [6, 8]

Property (Units)	Value	Standard Deviation
0° Flexural Strength (MPa)	2377.94	60.62
0° Flexural Modulus (GPa)	165.87	2.13
0° Maximum Strain (mm/mm)	1.46 e-2	3.85 e-4
90° Flexural Strength (MPa)	98.73	5.49
90° Flexural Modulus (GPa)	11.03	0.04
90° Maximum Strain (mm/mm)	8.64 e-3	5.24 e-4
AISS (MPa)	113.63	1.13
G_{IC} (J/m ²)	721.84	101.82
G_{IIC} (J/m ²)	1427	272

Dry powder prepregging has proven to be a successful technique for manufacturing 3kPETU/G30-500 towpreg that is flexible enough for in situ or on-line consolidation and could possibly be woven into fabrics. Furthermore, 3kPETU/G30-500 composite mechanical properties combined with PETU's excellent solvent resistance and thermo-oxidative stability produce a material well suited for high-performance applications.

CONCLUSION

Dry powder prepregging's ability to overcome the difficulties associated with high-melt viscosities increases the pool of viable polymers for high-performance FRPC applications. Three projects have been presented demonstrating the ability to produce towpreg and ultimately manufacture advanced composite materials from high-melt viscosity polymers. The MDPPS was implemented to study processing characteristics of two well-established semi-crystalline thermoplastic materials and investigate the manufacture and mechanical properties of a novel, crosslinkable, amorphous thermoplastic. Several questions were brought forward concerning the effects of powder particle size distribution on the processing of composites from PEEK/G30-500 towpreg. Optimal consolidation pressure and hold time were determined for GR-01 PPS/G30-500 composites. Finally, composites with good mechanical properties were manufactured from 3kPETU/G30-500 towpreg demonstrating this polymer is an excellent candidate for high-performance composite applications.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to thank the National Science Foundation Science and Technology Center for High Performance Polymeric Adhesives and Composites for support under contract DMR 91-20004. Appreciation goes to the Department of Defense National Defense Science and Engineering Graduate Research Fellowship Program and the Virginia Space Grant Consortium Aerospace Graduate Research Fellowship Program. The work of the following people was invaluable: Mike Mathews, Kedzie Davis, Jeremy Morin, and Rakesh Mehta.

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